

Quantitation of aristolochic acid using high performance liquid chromatography with photodiode array detection

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A rapid, sensitive and reproducible HPLC method with photodiode array detection for quantitative determination of aristolochic acid in plant sample is described. The procedure involves the extraction of aristolochic acid with methanol and chromatographic separation with a mobile phase of acetonitrile-water-trifluoroacetic acid-tetrahydrofuran. The average recovery of aristolochic acid is 97.8%. The minimum detectable concentration is 0.10 µg/injection of 5 µl injection volume.

The chief principle of the drug *Aristolochia indica* root is aristolochic acid which possesses a wide range of activities including antifeedant, insecticidal, antitumor, immuno modulating and antifertility activities¹. The reported HPLC methods² suffer with the drawback of high retention of compounds in the column, unsymmetrical peak and lack of peak purity. In continuation of our work on developing chromatographic procedures for plant drug analysis³ using photodiode array (PDA) detection, we report herein a rapid and sensitive reversed phase HPLC method for quantitation of aristolochic acid using a PDA detector.

Results and Discussion

Use of reported solvent system (MeOH-acetic acid-H₂O) resulted in broad and impure peak of aristolochic acid. Different compositions of acetonitrile in H₂O with TFA, acetic acid and THF were tried as mobile phase and finally optimized as acetonitrile-water-TFA-THF (50 : 50 : 1 : 1, v/v/v/v), which provided a good resolution of aristolochic acid to other peaks. A base line separation was observed in a 15 min run time. The results are presented in Table 1. Use of TFA in place of acetic acid resulted in a better peak purity of aristolochic acid peak. Addition of THF as modifier resulted a sharp peak of the compound. Peak corresponding to aristolochic acid, checked via addition of standard, was symmetrical. A better peak purity, similarity, resolution and sharp peak results were observed by using the mobile phase in HPLC as acetonitrile-water-TFA-THF (50 : 50 : 1 : 1, v/v/v/v). Recovery of the compound, calculated by addition of aristolochic acid in root extract, was found to be 97.8 ± 1.5%.

Table 1. Peak purity, similarity and column performance data for aristolochic acid in different HPLC mobile phases

Sl. no.	Mobile phase	Peak similarity	Peak purity		Column performance	
			Up	Down	Capacity factor	No. of theoretical plate counts
1.	Acetonitrile-H ₂ O-TFA (50 : 50 : 1)	0.9997	0.9996	0.9986	3.78	7565
2.	Acetonitrile-H ₂ O-AA (50 : 50 : 1)	0.9998	0.9995	0.9999	3.70	7137
3.	Acetonitrile-H ₂ O-AA-THF (50 : 50 : 1 : 1)	0.9996	0.9990	0.9998	3.51	7197
4.	Acetonitrile-H ₂ O-TFA-THF (50 : 50 : 1 : 1)	0.9999	0.9999	0.9999	3.56	7668

Linearity was determined in a working range of 2–20 µg of aristolochic acid using number of data points, 5; number of replicates, 3. It was $Y = 692.59 X + 15.238$ ($r = 0.999$). The values indicate a good linearity in the examined concentration range. Detection limit, determined by estimating the minimal mass of aristolochic acid that can be quantified, was 0.10 µg/injection of the compound.

Aristolochic acid content, estimated in different plant part of *A. indica* using the above procedure, were 0.017, 0.007 and 0.034% in leaves, stem and root respectively.

The proposed method is simple, rapid and accurate for the analysis of aristolochic acid in the plant *A. indica*. The method is suitable for the rapid screening in the genetical improvement experiments for the better isolation of aristolochic acid containing *A. indica* plant.

Experimental

Aristolochic acid was isolated from the plant *A. indica*, grown at C.I.M.A.P., Lucknow. Its identification was confirmed by comparison with a sample of aristolochic acid. All solvents used were of HPLC-grade (JT Baker).

A Shimadzu LC-8A gradient HPLC instrument, controlled by CBM-10A interface module, was used. A Shimadzu SPD-M10AVP PDA detector was used for peak purity test and analysis of aristolochic acid. A Class LC-10 workstation was used for data collection and analysis. Samples were injected through a Rheodyne 7725 I injector. A Millipore filtration unit was used. Analysis was performed on a Waters Spherisorb S10 ODS2 column (250 × 4.6 mm, i.d. 10 µm). Chromatographic operating conditions were : acetonitrile-water-TFA-THF (50 : 50 : 1 : 1, v/v/v/v); flow rate, 1.0 ml/min; column temperature, 26°; detector wavelength, 230 nm.

A 1 mg/5 ml solution in methanol of standard aristolochic acid was used during analysis. For the preparation of sample solution, powdered plant (1 g) was extracted using methanol (3 × 25 ml), filtered, concentrated, dried

under reduced pressure and made up to 5 ml in methanol for analysis.

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